

LH was the largest among the tropical species of GLH. Under 16 LH, the development of both sexes of NM was significantly shorter than under other photoperiods.

Among the four species, only the temperate NC showed a clear lengthening of nymphal development under 10 LH. Under 8 LH, both the 4th- and the 5th-instar nymphs of NC exhibited arrested development; total development was prolonged to 74.2 d for males and 77.9 d for females. □

Developmental period of *Nephotettix* spp. exposed to different photoperiods at 20 °C. Japan.

Species		Developmental period ^a (d)				
		8 LH	10 LH	12 LH	14 LH	16 LH
<i>N. nigropictus</i>	Male	43.8 a	44.3 a	42.0 c	42.8 bc	42.3 c
	Female	46.3 a	46.4 a	44.1 b	44.4 b	44.0 b
<i>N. virescens</i>	Male	44.0 a	44.3 a	42.4 a	41.2 a	42.3 a
	Female	45.6 a	45.2 a	44.2 a	42.7 b	40.8 c
<i>N. cincticeps</i>	Male	74.2 a	55.2 b	44.0 c	39.6 d	40.4 d
	Female	77.9 a	58.6 b	43.7 c	42.8 c	42.9 c
<i>N. malayanus</i>	Male	44.1 a	43.8 a	43.6 a	42.7 a	40.3 b
	Female	46.7 a	46.1 a	45.3 a	45.3 a	43.4 b

^aIn a row, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

An earwig predator of Asian pink stem borer (PSB) in upland rice

A. T. Barrion, E.M. Libetario, and J.A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

Asian PSB *Sesamia inferens* (Walker) can be particularly abundant in upland rice grown near sugarcane or related grasses. We found the earwig *Euborellia stali* (Dohrn) preying on PSB larva in stem borer-damaged tillers in upland ricefields in Claveria, northern Mindanao, Philippines. The predatory earwig bites the anal portion as the larva attempts to escape. There is a similar record of this earwig preying on the Oriental maize borer *Ostrinia furnacalis* (Guenée).

E. stali (see figure) has a shiny black body, light yellow brown legs with a black band on midfemora, and 17-segmented antennae with segments 14-15 colored white. It is common in dryland habitats and can be collected by digging in the soil at the base of rice hills.

The female earwig drags its prey out of the stem to her nest at the base of the plant to feed the newly hatched nymphs. A female shows maternal care to the 200-350 pale yellow and globular eggs it lays.

The nocturnal earwigs live 3-5 mo. Cage studies show that this earwig can consume 20-30 young PSB larvae a day. □

Adult of *E. stali* (a) and its feeding behavior on PSB larva inside the plant stem (b). Scale = 1 mm.

Ovicidal activity of eight insecticides against the rice whorl maggot (RWM) *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino

P. C. Pantua and J. A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

Two-wk-old potted rice plants were caged in nylon mesh. Field-collected male and female RWM adults were introduced into the cage and allowed to oviposit. Eggs on each potted plant were counted at 1 d. Plants with at least 10 eggs were used in the experiment.

Four potted plants laden with 2-d-old RWM eggs were placed in a mylar cage and sprayed with 25 ml (equivalent to spray water volume of

Ovicidal activity of 8 insecticides applied as foliar spray on plants with 2-d-old eggs of RWM. IRRI, 1986.

Insecticide	Formulation	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Egg mortality ^a (%)
Deltamethrin	2.5 EC	0.012	98 a
Triazophos	40 EC	0.4	97 a
Azinphos-ethyl	40 EC	0.4	94 a
BPMC	50 EC	0.4	50 b
Carbaryl	85 WP	0.4	42 b
Carbosulfan	20 EC	0.4	39 b
Buprofezin	25 WP	0.125	32 b
Malathion	51 EC	0.4	25 b

^aAv of replications. All means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Abbott's formula was applied for corrected percent egg mortality.

1,000 liters/ ha) of each test insecticide using a 1-liter plastic hand sprayer.

Deltamethrin, triazophos, and azinphos-ethyl were highly ovicidal

(see table). Some ovicidal activity occurred with BPMC, carbaryl, carbosulfan, buprofezin, and malathion. □